

A light-trap survey of the abundance and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers in Egypt

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Leafhoppers and planthoppers were surveyed in rice fields at Kafr-el-Sheikh, northern Egypt, with a light trap operated 2 nights/week throughout 1974–1975. Twelve species of the Cicadellidae family, six of Delphacidae, and one species each of Cixiidae and Meenoplidae families were trapped. Considerably more insects were caught in 1975 than in 1974 — 129.4 vs 83.2 Cicadellidae/night and 134.6 vs 121.2

Delphacidae/night. The highest monthly averages were in June and July for *Empoasca decipiens* and *Macrosteles sexnotatus*; August and September for *Balclutha hortensis*, *Cicadulina bipunctella zaeae*, *Exitianus taeniaticeps*, *Balclutha rufofasciata*, *Neolimninus aegyptiacus*, and *Orosius albicinctus*; and October for *Nephotettix modulatus* and *Recilia schmidtgeni*. The monthly averages for delphacids were highest in September and October.

The sex ratio in the light-trap catches was near equality (44–54% males) in *N. aegyptiacus*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Falctoya aglauros*, *Matutinus iphias*, *Perkinsiella insignis*, and *Oliarus frontalis*. But males were more prominent (57–70%) in *E. taeniaticeps*, *Sogatella vibix*, and *Nisia atrovonosa*. The male catch was much lower (< 40%) in the other species.

The relative abundance and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers caught in lit trap in rice fields, Kafr-el Sheikh, Egypt, 1974–75.

Family and species	Av. no./night		Peak no./night ^a		Females (av. %) 1974–75
	1974	1975	1974	1975	
<i>Family Cicadellidae</i>					
<i>Balclutha hortensis</i>	40.5	50.6	308.3	258.6	37.6
<i>Cicadulina bipunctella zaeae</i>	20.0	36.2	162.3	176.8	34.8
<i>Empoasca decipiens</i>	12.3	30.1	83.3	211.8	23.5
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i>	6.4	6.6	38.9	46.6	30.2
<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	1.2	3.1	5.7	21.9	20.0
<i>Exitianus taeniaticeps</i>	1.4	1.6	3.4	6.8	57.3
<i>Recilia schmidtgeni</i>	0.8	0.6	5.0	2.4	34.2
<i>Balclutha rufofasciata</i>	0.3	0.3	1.3	1.3	39.7
<i>Neolimninus aegyptiacus</i>	0.2	0.2	1.0	0.9	43.8
<i>Orosius albicinctus</i>	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.4	14.3
<i>Batrachomorphus signatus</i>	0.0	0.1	0.4	0.7	—
<i>Neolaliturus haematoceps</i>	0.0	0.01	0.0	0.1	—
Total	83.2	129.4	522.7	457.0	—
<i>Family Delphacidae</i>					
<i>Sogatella vibix</i>	108.7	120.7	1,009.1	908.0	64.8
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	6.1	7.2	37.1	41.1	53.8
<i>Toya nigeriensis</i>	3.3	3.0	22.1	20.1	38.7
<i>Falctoya aglauros</i>	2.4	2.9	17.5	22.2	49.5
<i>Matutinus iphias</i>	0.4	0.5	2.2	3.7	54.4
<i>Perkinsiella insignis</i>	0.3	0.3	1.6	2.1	46.7
Total	121.2	134.6	1,088.5	997.2	—
<i>Family Cixiidae</i>					
<i>Oliarus frontalis</i>	0.7	0.5	2.9	2.7	51.6
<i>Family Meenoplidae</i>					
<i>Nisia atrovonosa</i>	0.2	0.2	1.1	0.8	70.2

^aMonthly average.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides for brown planthopper control

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* injects its eggs into the tissues of rice leaf sheaths, making contact with insecticides difficult. Because most insecticides have short residual activity, control of the nymphs that hatch a few days after application is poor. Such nymphs may increase BPH populations after spraying. Consequently, the proper timing of insecticide application is of utmost importance. But before growers can achieve it, they must be trained to monitor BPH populations. Application timing would be less critical if insecticides that act as ovicides (i.e. that cause egg mortality) as well as kill BPH nymphs and adults are used.

The ovicidal activity of several insecticides commonly used for rice pest control was studied at IRRI. BPH were allowed to oviposit on plants for 24 hours. At 1 day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with a 0.04% concentration of the insecticides BPMC,

Comparative hatchability of brown planthopper eggs at different ages when different concentrations of carbofuran are used. IRRI, 1976.

carbofuran, dimethoate, metalkamate, methyl parathion, MIPC, propoxur, and triazophos. Nymphs were removed daily and counted. At 14 days after oviposition, the plants were dissected and the unhatched eggs counted. Carbofuran, triazophos, and methyl parathion reduced egg hatches significantly. No eggs hatched in the carbofuran treatment. Egg hatch

was 37% in the triazophos treatment and 61% in methyl parathion. Further studies indicated that insecticide concentration and age of egg at time of application influenced ovicidal activity (see figure). Five-day-old eggs were more susceptible than 1- and 3-day-old eggs. Concentrations of 0.04 and 0.02% had ovicidal activity on 1-day-old eggs, but concentrations of

0.01 and 0.005% had none.

Another study indicated that granular carbofuran, metalkamate, triazophos, and diazinon at 1 kg a.i./ha in paddy water applied to potted plants containing 1-day-old eggs had ovicidal activity. Carbofuran, metalkamate, and triazophos caused 100% egg mortality. **W**

Base vs canopy insecticide spray for brown planthopper control

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Foliar spray is the most common method of applying insecticide for the control of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* in the tropics. Because the BPH feeds at the base of the plant, Philippine control recommendations specify that the spray be directed toward the base of the plant—a time-consuming and laborious application method for spraying large areas.

Sprays directed to the base and to the canopy of the plant were compared in three IRRI experiments in 1977. In the first 2 experiments, Perthane was 10 to 20% more effective as a base spray than as a canopy spray. In a third experiment, the two methods were compared using metalkamate, monocrotophos, and Perthane. Perthane sprayed at the base of plants controlled BPH significantly better than when sprayed above the canopy (95 vs 63% control) (see table).

Foliar application of insecticides applied above and below the rice canopy for brown planthopper (BPH) control. IRRI, 1977.

Insecticide ^a	BPH (no./4linear-m row) ^b sampled with D-Vac suction machine		
	Before insecticide application (no.)	2 days after application (no.)	Control ^c (%)
<i>Applied above the rice canopy</i>			
Metalkamate	4,766 a	1,183 a	74
Monocrotophos	8,213 a	3,168 b	60
Perthane	7,342 a	2,589 b	63
No insecticide	6,190 a	5,893 b	5
<i>Applied below the rice canopy</i>			
Metalkamate	11,241 a	947 a	92
Monocrotophos	6,723 a	2,074 b	69
Perthane	7,521 a	335 a	96
No insecticide	7,805 a	8,811 c	0

^aHopper development was induced by foliar application of 30 g a.i. decamethrin/ha starting at 15 days after transplanting. Three applications were made at 750 g a.i./ha. The volume of spray material for both methods was 1,444 liters/ha.

^bIn each column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^cValues shown were adjusted using Abbott's formula.

Metalkamate and monocrotophos sprayed at the base controlled BPH slightly—but not significantly—better than when sprayed above the canopy.

In other 1977 IRRI studies, monocrotophos sprayed only on the leaves controlled BPH feeding on the leaf

sheaths at the base of the plant. That indicates that some insecticides move downward from the upper leaf area to the leaf sheath. The desirability of spraying below the canopy may depend on the insecticide applied. **W**

Contact toxicity of insecticides to the three biotypes of brown planthopper

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In recent years the population of biotype 2 of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* has increased in farmers' fields in Indonesia and the Philippines. Biotype 2 destroys IR26, which carries the *Bph 1* gene for resistance. In IRRI greenhouse

experiments another biotype, biotype 3, emerged when BPH were forced to feed on such varieties as IR32 that carry the *bph 2* gene for resistance derived from ASD 7. So far biotype 3 has not become abundant in farmers' fields. It is important to know whether a change in biotype predominance in the natural population will also result in a change in susceptibility to the various insecticides.

Previous studies indicated that of the three biotypes, biotype 1 was generally most susceptible to various insecticides

when feeding on rice plants in paddy water treated with granular formulations. In this study the contact toxicity of insecticides to the three biotypes was determined. The insecticides were applied as sprays to the insects using Potter's spray tower.

Results indicated that biotype 1 was least susceptible to the commonly used insecticides carbofuran, metalkamate, diazinon, and methyl parathion (see table). There was no significant difference among biotypes in the decamethrin and